

FORMULATION, CHARACTERIZATION & OPTIMIZATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCH OF CURCUMIN

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ABSTRACT

Transdermal drug delivery systems are defined as self-contained, discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug(s), through the skin, at a controlled rate to the systemic circulation. Transdermal delivery can provide a number of advantages over conventional methods of drug administration, including enhanced efficacy, increased safety, greater convenience and improved patient compliance. By delivering a steady flow of drugs into the blood stream over an extended period of time, Transdermal systems can avoid the “peak” and “valley” effect of or injectable therapy and can enable more controlled, effective treatment. By avoiding first pass metabolism through the gastrointestinal tract and the liver, the therapeutically equivalent dosage for the Transdermal delivery of certain compounds can be significantly less than the corresponding oral dosage, potentially reducing dosage related side effects. Transdermal therapeutic systems are designed for controlled drug delivery through the skin into systemic circulation maintaining consistent efficacy.

Keyword: -1.Transdermal, 2.Polymer, 3.Patch, etc....

1 INTRODUCTION

Discovering a new medicine is an extremely costly and time-consuming endeavor. However, reengineering the methods and systems used to deliver drugs into the body is a less risky and more profitable task. Designing dosage forms, such as tablets, injections, or patches, to deliver the correct amount of medicine at the precise time and to the specific target site becomes complex when each medication must be administered optimally and ideally tailored to each individual patient. The medication may not be absorbed if it is released too slowly. If it is delivered too rapidly, the patient may suffer untoward effects and its desired effect may not last as long as needed. If patient is expected to take the medicine more than two times a day, compliance will be adversely affected. Over the past two decades, significant progress has been made in controlled release drug delivery of therapeutic agent. Current technology has improved to such a level that delivery of certain drug at a constant rate over a period of time ranging from days to years is no longer a major problem. This mode of administration provides advantages over oral or injectable administration. It is less aggressive than injection and has the advantage of not forcing the drug through the tough environment of the gastrointestinal system. Furthermore, its dissemination through the circulatory system is less affected by liver and renal function. Transdermal drug delivery system is highly investigated new drug delivery system of a number of drugs and many Transdermal drug delivery systems of different drugs.

1.1 Sustained Release Concept

The conventional drug delivery systems are still the primary pharmaceutical products commonly seen today. To achieve and maintain the drug concentration in the body within the therapeutic range required for a medication, it is often necessary to take this type of drug delivery system several times a day. There are two approaches to overcome such situations: 1) Develop new, better and safer drugs with long half-lives and large therapeutic indices. 2) Effective and safer use of existing drugs through concepts and techniques of novel drug delivery systems. The need for certain drugs to be delivered at a preprogrammed rate over a prolonged period has led to the development of Transdermal therapeutic systems. This system provides drug systemically at a predictable rate and maintain the rate for extended period of time. Thus, elimination of numerous problems associated with bioavailability, enhanced first pass hepatic metabolisms relatively short residence time, dose inflexibility.

1.2 Several Controlled and Novel Drug Delivery Systems include:

Table 1- Several Controlled and Novel Drug Delivery Systems

Sr. No.	Name of System
1.	Oral Drug Delivery and Delivery System
2.	Ocular Drug Delivery and Delivery System
3.	Mucosal Drug Delivery and Delivery System
4.	Nasal Drug Delivery and Delivery System
5.	Parenteral Drug Delivery and Delivery System
6.	Vaginal Drug Delivery and Delivery System
7.	Transdermal Drug Delivery and Delivery System
8.	Intrauterine Drug Delivery and Delivery System
9.	Controlled Delivery of Vaccine

2. MATERIAL & METHODS

Table 2- Chemical & Reagent

Sr. No.	Chemical / Reagent / Solvent
1	Curcumin
2	EC and HPMC
3	Propylene Glycol
4	Oleic Acid
5	Ethanol
6	Glycerine

2.1 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1.1 Preparation of Standard Calibration Curve of Curcumin

The Calibration curve was plotted within the concentration range of 2-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of the drug using phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Accurately weighed 20 mg of curcumin was dissolved in phosphate

buffer and diluted up to 100 ml with buffer. From this solution 10 ml was withdrawn and again volume was made up to 100 ml with buffer. From this solution 1, 2, 3 up to 10 ml were withdrawn in separate volumetric flask and final volume was made up to 10 ml with buffer.

2.1.2 Investigation of Physicochemical Compatibility of Drug and Polymer

Fourier transforms infrared spectroscopy studies

Physicochemical compatibility between Curcumin and Polymers used in patches was studied by using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The infrared (IR) spectra were recorded using an FTIR spectrophotometer by the KBr pellet method and spectra were recorded in the wavelength region between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} . The Spectra obtained for curcumin, polymers and physical mixtures of Curcumin with polymers were compared.

Differential Scanning Colorimetry (DSC)

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the physical mixture was measured on a differential scanning calorimeter (Dell, Japan) at a heating rate of 10 $^\circ$ /min from -60 to 120 $^\circ$ C under nitrogen environment. The physical mixture must be dried in vacuum before analysis.

2.1.3 Development of Transdermal Patches

The matrix-type Transdermal patches were prepared by solvent casting method. The matrix-type Transdermal patches containing Curcumin were prepared using different ratio of HPMC and EC. The polymers in different ratio increased to a total weight of 850 mg and dissolved in ethanol⁸¹. The drug, Curcumin was added slowly to polymeric solution and mixed thoroughly to obtain a uniform solution using magnetic stirrer. Propylene Glycol was used a plasticizer. The polymeric solution (4ml) of drug was poured in to the glass ring (bangle) kept on to the mercury substrate. Then covered with an inverted funnel of suitable diameter to prevent atmospheric moisture and also to control the solvent evaporation⁸². It was stored in room temperature for 24 h. After complete evaporation of the solvent, the patch was removed. Patches of 2 cm^2 were cut and placed in desiccator with 0% RH till further evaluation.

Formulation Composition of Curcumin Polymeric Patches

The matrix-type controlled Transdermal Drug Delivery system were prepared by using polymers, plasticizers, permeation enhancers and drug.

2.1.4 Evaluation of Transdermal Patches Containing Curcumin

a. Physicochemical Properties of Transdermal Patches

The patches were evaluated for the following physicochemical properties:

i. Weight Variation

Weight variation was studied by individually weighing 4 randomly selected patches. Such determination was performed for each formulation.

ii. Thickness

The thickness was measured by means of electrometer (Ultrasonic coating thickness gauge, Model 446 FBS1). Each patch was measured for thickness at five different points.

iii. Folding Endurance

Folding endurance of patches was determined by repeatedly folding a small strip of patch at the same place till it breaks. The maximum number of folding operation done at the same place of the patch without breaking, give the value of folding endurance, where the cracking point of the patches were considered as the end point.

iv. Percentage Moisture Uptake

A weighed patch kept in a desiccator at room temperature for 24 h was taken out and exposed to 84 % relative humidity (a saturated solution of Potassium Chloride) in a desiccator until a constant weight for the patch was obtained. The percentage moisture uptake was calculated as the difference between final and initial weight with respect to initial weight.

v. Percentage Moisture Content

The patches were weighed individually and kept in a desiccator containing calcium chloride at room temperature for 24 h. Individual patches were weighed repeatedly until they showed a constant weight. The percentage of moisture content was calculated as the difference between initial and final weight with respect to final weight.

vi. Water Vapor Transmission Rate

For the study of water vapor transmission (WVT) rate, vials of equal diameter were used as transmission cell. These cells were washed thoroughly and dried in an oven. Calcium chloride (1 g) was taken in the cell and the polymeric patches measuring 2 cm² area was fixed over the brim with the help of an adhesive. The cells were weighed accurately and initial weight is recorded, and then kept in a closed desiccator containing saturated solution of potassium chloride (200 ml). The humidity inside the desiccator was measured by a hygrometer and it was found to be 84 %. The cells were taken out and weighed after 24 h. From increase in weights the amount of water transmitted and the rate at which water vapor transmitted were calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{WVT rate} = \text{WL/S}$$

Where,

W= Water Vapor Transmitted in Grams,

L= Thickness of the patch in cm

S= Exposed surface area in cm²

vii. Drug Content of Patches

A measured patch (2 cm²) was cut into small pieces, put into a 100 ml phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4), and the solution was stirred with teflon coated magnetic bead on magnetic stirrer continuously for 24 h. The contents were filtered using whatman filter paper and the filtrate was examined for the drug content against the reference solution consisting of placebo patch (containing no drug) spectrophotometrically at 224.8 nm.

b. In-vitro Drug Release Studies

Conducting a drug-release study of the patch is essential to ensure the drug concentration at the surface of the stratum corneum is greater than the drug concentration in the body to achieve a constant rate of permeation through diffusion. The paddle over disc method was employed for assessment of the release of the drug from the prepared patches. In vitro drug release study was conducted using a USP paddle type dissolution apparatus. The dry patch of known thickness were cut into circular shape, weighed, and fixed over a glass plate with an adhesive. The plate was then placed in a 900 ml phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), and apparatus was equilibrated to 32° ± 0.4° 90. The paddle was then set at a distance of 2.4 cm from the glass plate and operated at a

speed of 100 rpm. A sample (4 ml) was withdrawn at various time intervals up to 12 h and 24 h and replaced with same amount of phosphate buffer. Samples were analyzed for drug content at 224.8 nm using double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer.

c. In-vitro Drug Permeation Studies

In vitro drug permeation studies were carried out using modified franz diffusion cells, made up of glass⁶⁶. The capacity of receptor compartment was 20 ml. The area of donor compartment exposed to receptor compartment was 4.30 cm². The cellophane membrane was used for permeation studies. The cellophane membrane was previously soaked for 24 h in phosphate buffer⁸⁴. The cellophane membrane was sandwiched between the receptor compartment and donar compartment. The one side of cellophane membrane was kept in intimate contact with the release surface of TDDS and mounted between the donar and the receptor compartment. The receptor medium was phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and maintained at 37°±1°. The heat was provided using a thermostatic hot plate with a magnetic stirrer at 40 rpm. The receptor fluid was stirred by a Teflon coated magnetic bead fitted to a magnetic stirrer. At various time interval, samples were withdrawn at regular period through the sampling port and were replaced by equal volume of fresh receptor fluid. The samples withdrawn were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 224.8 nm.

3. RESULT & DISCUSSION

3.1 Preparation of standard calibration curve of Curcumin

The calibration curve was plotted within the concentration range of 2-20 µg/ml of the drug using phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Accurately weighed 20 mg of curcumin was dissolved in phosphate buffer and diluted up to 100 ml with buffer. From this solution 10 ml was withdrawn and again volume was made up to 100 ml with buffer. From this solution 1, 2, 3 up to 10 ml were withdrawn in separate volumetric flask and final volume was made up to 10 ml with buffer. Absorbance was noted at 224.8 nm, since maximum absorbance was observed at this wavelength. The standard calibration curve of Curcumin at pH 7.4 was shown Figure.8. Drug concentration and absorbance followed linear relationship the curve obeyed Beer's-Lambert's law within concentration range 2-20 µg/ml.

Table 3- Drug Concentration and Absorbance

Sr.No.	Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance(425nm)
1	2	0.106
2	4	0.188
3	6	0.266
4	8	0.341
5	10	0.440
6	12	0.497
7	14	0.590

Sr.No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance(425nm)
8	16	0.667
9	18	0.740
10	20	0.854

Figure 1- Standard calibration curve of Curcumin in buffer pH 7.4

3.2 Investigation of physicochemical compatibility of drug and polymer

a. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy studies

Physicochemical compatibility between Curcumin and polymers used in the patches was studied by using fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The infrared (IR) spectra were recorded using an FTIR spectrophotometer by the KBr pellet method and spectra were recorded in the wavelength region between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} . The spectra obtained for Curcumin, polymers and physical mixtures of Curcumin with polymers were compared.

Figure 2- IR Spectra of Curcumin Pure

Figure 3- IR Spectra of EC

Table 4 FTIR Spectral Analysis

IR of drug and polymer mixture	Principle peaks of IR
Curcumin	3533, 3411-3359, 3282-3263, 3085, 3028, 2979, 2966, 2954, 2860, 2819, 2796, 1620, 1530, 1506, 1438, 1396, 1380, 1310, 1244, 1197, 1149, 1132, 1085, 1076, 1029, 989, 950, 910, 838, 617 cm^{-1} .
EC and HPMC	3450, 2960-2840, 2380, 1720, 1490, 1400, 1150, 1050, 950, 850, 750 cm^{-1} .

b. Differential Scanning Colorimetry

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the physical mixture was measured on a differential scanning calorimeter (Dell, Japan) at a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$ from -60 to 120° under nitrogen environment. The physical mixture must be dried in vacuum before analysis.

3.3 Development of Transdermal Patches

The matrix-type Transdermal patches were prepared by solvent casting method. The matrix-type Transdermal patches containing Curcumin were prepared using different ratio of HPMC and EC. The polymers in different ratio increased to a total weight of 850 mg and dissolved in ethanol 81. The drug, Curcumin was added slowly to polymeric solution and mixed thoroughly to obtain a uniform solution using magnetic stirrer. Propylene Glycol was used a plasticizer. The polymeric solution (4ml) of drug was poured in to the glass ring (bangle) kept on to the mercury substrate. Then covered with an inverted funnel of suitable diameter to prevent atmospheric moisture and also to control the solvent evaporation. It was stored in room temperature for 24 h. After complete evaporation of the solvent, the patch was removed. Patches of 2 cm^2 were cut and placed in dessicator with 0% RH till further evaluation.

3.4 Formulation Composition of Curcumin Polymeric Patches

The matrix-type controlled Transdermal drug delivery systems were prepared by using polymers, plasticizer, permeation enhancers and drug.

Figure 4-Lab Scale Assembly for preparation of Transdermal Patches

3.5 Evaluation of Transdermal Patches Containing Curcumin

3.5.1 Physicochemical Properties of Transdermal Patches

The patches were evaluated for the following physicochemical properties:

i. Weight Variation

Weight variation was studied by individually weighing 4 randomly selected patches. Such determination was performed for each formulation.

Table 5 Weight Variation of Patches

Sr. No.	Formulation	Weight(mg)				Average weight(mg)
1	F1	34	31	34	33	33.24±1.71
2	F2	34	33	36	32	33.74±1.71
3	F3	28	33	36	37	33.40±4.04
4	F4	34	36	41	41	38.24±3.20
4	F4	31	33	38	39	34.24±3.86
6	F6	28	31	34	36	32.40±3.70
7	F7	32	33	34	39	34.74±3.10
8	F8	27	33	34	31	31.4±3.42
9	F9	32	37	34	36	34.40±2.08

Each Value represents mean ±SD (n=4)

ii. Thickness

The thickness was measured by means of electrometer (Ultrasonic coating thickness gauge, Model 446 FBS1). Each patch was measured for thickness at five different points.

iii. Folding Endurance (a measure of fragility)

Folding endurance of patches was determined by repeatedly folding a small strip of patch at the same place till it breaks. The maximum number of folding operation done at the same place of the patch without breaking, give the value of folding endurance, where the cracking point of the patches were considered as the end point.

iv. Percentage Moisture Uptake

A weighed patch kept in a desiccator at room temperature for 24 h was taken out and exposed to 84 % relative humidity (a saturated solution of Potassium Chloride) in a desiccator until a constant weight for the patch was obtained. The percentage moisture uptake was calculated as the difference between final and initial weight with respect to initial weight.

Figure 5- Average percentage of moisture uptake of different formulations

v. Percentage Moisture Content

The patches were weighed individually and kept in a desiccator containing calcium chloride at room temperature for 24 h. Individual patches were weighed repeatedly until they showed a constant weight. The percentage of moisture content was calculated as the difference between initial and final weight with respect to final weight.

vi. Water Vapour Transmission Rate

For the study of water vapour transmission (WVT) rate, vials of equal diameter were used as transmission cell. These cells were washed thoroughly and dried in an oven. Calcium chloride (1 g) was taken in the cell and the polymeric patches measuring 2 cm² area was fixed over the brim with the help of an adhesive. The cells were weighed accurately and initial weight is recorded, and then kept in a closed desiccator containing saturated solution of potassium chloride (200 ml). The humidity inside the desiccator was measured by a hygrometer and it was found to be 84 %. The cells were taken out and weighed after 24 h. From increase in weights the amount of water transmitted and the rate at which water vapour transmitted were calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{WVT rate} = \text{WL/S}$$

Where,

W= Water Vapour Transmitted in grams,

L= Thickness of the patch in cm,

S= Exposed surface area in cm².

Table 6- Water Vapour Transmission rate of Patches

Sr.No.	Formulation	Thickness (μm)	WVTR g/cm ² .24h
1	F1	39.00 \pm 2.64	1.26 \times 10 ⁻⁴
2	F2	33.67 \pm 1.42	1.14 \times 10 ⁻⁴
3	F3	36.67 \pm 3.21	1.20 \times 10 ⁻⁴
4	F4	34.67 \pm 3.78	1.04 \times 10 ⁻⁴
4	F4	39.33 \pm 1.42	1.16 \times 10 ⁻⁴
6	F6	38.33 \pm 3.04	1.27 \times 10 ⁻⁴
7	F7	38.33 \pm 2.41	1.30 \times 10 ⁻⁴
8	F8	36.33 \pm 2.08	1.24 \times 10 ⁻⁴
9	F9	36.33 \pm 2.08	1.43 \times 10 ⁻⁴

Each Value represents mean \pm SD(n=3)

vii.

Drug Content of patches

A measured patch (2 cm²) was cut into small pieces, put into a 100 ml phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4), and the solution was stirred with teflon coated magnetic bead on magnetic stirrer continuously for 24 h. The contents were filtered using whatman filter paper and the filtrate was examined for the drug content against the reference solution consisting of placebo patch (containing no drug) spectrophotometrically at 224.8 nm.

Table 7- Drug Content of Patches

Sr.No.	Formulation	Thickness (μm)	Drugcontent	
			%/Patch	mg/Patch
1	F1	33 \pm 1.02	88.14 \pm 2.11	4.42
2	F2	42 \pm 1.42	94.42 \pm 1.64	4.71
3	F3	43 \pm 0.64	74.72 \pm 2.01	3.74
4	F4	44 \pm 1.44	97.42 \pm 1.40	4.87
4	F4	49 \pm 1.14	74.23 \pm 0.92	3.84

Sr.No.	Formulation	Thickness (μm)	Drugcontent	
			%/Patch	mg/Patch
6	F6	37 \pm 1.37	97.74 \pm 1.34	4.41
7	F7	34 \pm 1.04	90.66 \pm 2.18	4.43
8	F8	33 \pm 1.44	92.73 \pm 2.10	4.64
9	F9	36 \pm 1.84	88.07 \pm 1.00	4.40

Each value represents mean \pm SD (n=3)

3.5.2 In-vitro Drug Release Studies

Conducting a drug-release study of the patch is essential to ensure the drug concentration at the surface of the stratum corneum is greater than the drug concentration in the body to achieve a constant rate of permeation through diffusion. The paddle over disc method was employed for assessment of the release of the drug from the prepared patches. In vitro drug release study was conducted using a USP paddle type dissolution apparatus. The dry patch of known thickness were cut into circular shape, weighed, and fixed over a glass plate with an adhesive. The plate was then placed in a 900 ml phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), and apparatus was equilibrated to 32 $^{\circ}$ \pm 0.4 $^{\circ}$ 90. The paddle was then set at a distance of 2.4 cm from the glass plate and operated at a speed of 100 rpm. A sample (4 ml) was withdrawn at various time intervals up to 12 h and 24 h and replaced with same amount of phosphate buffer. Samples were analyzed for drug content at 224.8 nm using double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer.

Table 8- Drug Release Data of Prepared Transdermal Patches

Sample	Time (hrs)												
	Cumulative % drug released												
	1	2	3	4	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	24
F1	26.14 \pm 0.91	33.73 \pm 1.44	39.77 \pm 0.94	44.14 \pm 1.94	46.47 \pm 0.96	47.64 \pm 1.26	60.41 \pm 2.17	63.67 \pm 2.13	72.84 \pm 1.80	80.17 \pm 2.03	81.14 \pm 2.41	91.14 \pm 3.37	94.13 \pm 3.12
F2	37.42 \pm 2.27	40.21 \pm 1.44	41.19 \pm 1.44	47.47 \pm 1.04	49.74 \pm 1.10	60.40 \pm 2.10	62.01 \pm 3.01	72.32 \pm 2.10	76.19 \pm 3.88	83.29 \pm 2.03	82.82 \pm 1.08	87.68 \pm 2.10	89.89 \pm 1.08
F3	33.98 \pm 1.20	38.66 \pm 2.20	42.44 \pm 1.23	49.16 \pm 2.12	43.80 \pm 1.14	44.98 \pm 1.14	44.66 \pm 2.06	46.43 \pm 1.12	46.79 \pm 1.72	62.68 \pm 1.14	68.62 \pm 1.94	71.04 \pm 1.02	74.04 \pm 1.03
F4	23.71 \pm 1.20	34.1 \pm 2.09	44.6 \pm 1.20	41.06 \pm 1.04	42.3 \pm 1.16	49.4 \pm 2.14	67,31 \pm 2.16	70.49 \pm 1.33	74.99 \pm 1.08	83.2 \pm 1.91	87.49 \pm 2.03	89.3 \pm 2.28	94.22 \pm 0.98

F4	24.97 ± 1.10	32.29 ± 1.02	47.11 ± 2.08	41.61 ± 2.20	49.40 ± 2.30	48.41 ± 1.31	60.17 ± 2.13	77.48 ± 1.04	78.88 ± 1.46	81.74 ± 1.11	81.61 ± 4.06	84.24 ± 1.12	91.24 ± 1.14
F6	34.10 ±1.09	39.64 ±1.04	47.47 ±1.16	43.60 ±1.16	44.94 ±1.97	47.92 ±1.98	43.28 ±1.14	64.76 ±1.46	66.77 ±2.16	72.99 ±2.07	73.63 ±2.13	78.23 ± 0.97	98.66 ± 1.10
F7	29.03 ±1.02	46.02 ±1.01	40.38 ±1.07	47.91 ± 2.24	44.03 ± 2.01	60.14 ± 0.94	60.41 ± 1.24	64.99 ± 1.08	73.94 ± 1.18	77.88 ± 2.03	80.88 ± 1.08	83.14 ± 2.00	87.17 ± 2.11
F8	11.87 ± 2.09	34.22 ± 0.97	41.84 ± 0.92	42.40 ± 2.10	44.43 ± 1.19	49.24 ± 1.14	42.92 ± 2.08	49.89 ± 1.08	64.48 ± 1.03	71.79 ± 1.14	83.19 ± 2.12	84.67 ± 1.21	92.26 ± 2.12
F9	26.14 ± 0.97	39.48 ± 1.02	41.16 ± 2.11	39.81 ± 0.94	46.48 ± 2.02	47.48 ± 0.10	64.68 ± 2.13	63.24 ± 2.14	74.37 ± 2.10	77.34 ± 2.04	78.17 ± 2.01	82.60 ± 0.89	94.26 ± 2.12

Each value represents mean \pm SD (n=3)

3.5.3 In-vitro Drug Permeation Studies

In vitro drug permeation studies were carried out using modified franz diffusion cells, made up of glass⁶⁶. The capacity of receptor compartment was 20 ml. The area of donor compartment exposed to receptor compartment was 4.30 cm². The cellophane membrane was used for permeation studies. The cellophane membrane was previously soaked for 24 h in phosphate buffer⁸⁴. The cellophane membrane was sandwiched between the receptor compartment and donor compartment. The one side of cellophane membrane was kept in intimate contact with the release surface of TDDS and mounted between the donor and the receptor compartment. The receptor medium was phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and maintained at 37° \pm 1°. The heat was provided using a thermostatic hot plate with a magnetic stirrer at 40 rpm. The receptor fluid was stirred by a teflon coated magnetic bead fitted to a magnetic stirrer. At various time intervals, samples were withdrawn at regular period through the sampling port and were replaced by equal volume of fresh receptor fluid. The samples withdrawn were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 224.8 nm.

Table 9- Drug Permeation Data of Prepared Transdermal Patches

Sample	Time (hrs)												
	Cumulative % drug released												
	1	2	3	4	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	24
F1	3.28± 1.18	9.142 ± 1.09	11.47 ± 2.20	17.87 ± 2.09	22.73 ± 2.12	23.70 ± 2.10	26.72 ± 2.13	33.18 ± 1.13	39.73 ± 1.12	48.36 ± 1.12	44.78 ± 1.08	66.20 ± 2.14	77.30 ± 2.01
F2	4.28± 2.03	8.98± 2.09	14.48 ± 1.02	23.66 ± 1.06	29.78 ±1.10	36.02 ± 0.98	42.37 ± 2.10	49.38 ± 1.11	64.74 ± 2.04	70.14 ± 40.12	74.28 ± 1.04	89.91 ± 4.82	92.20 ± 2.12

F3	4.37± 2.10	9.94± 1.03	14.61 ± 2.01	24.73 ± 2.10	30.90 ± 2.09	37.19 ± 1.09	43.49 ± 2.04	40.64 ± 0.96	62.19 ± 1.09	67.43 ± 3.88	73.39 ± 2.14	78.92 ±1.09	87.20 ± 2.12
F4	10.78 ± 2.14	14.21 ± 2.11	17.18 ± 1.09	18.41 ± 1.12	23.34 ± 1.04	34.00 ± 1.00	41.32 ± 1.10	47.48 ± 2.18	43.48 ± 1.03	48.12 ± 1.08	68.17 ± 1.10	71.96 ± 0.98	81.32 ± 2.10
F5	4.86± 1.87	9.261 ± 2.11	13.37 ± 2.09	14.74 ± 1.11	21.64 ±1.14	20.83 ± 1.07	29.43 ± 2.30	36.40 ± 1.10	42.84 ± 1.09	41.74 ± 1.26	60.31 ± 2.11	67.01 ± 2.03	83.02 ± 1.02
F6	13.40 ± 1.10	18.93 ± 1.04	30.16 ± 2.12	36.04 ± 1.03	42.67 ± 2.04	49.43 ± 2.31	48.26 ± 1.11	62.98 ± 2.70	67.19 ± 2.09	70.44 ± 1.14	70.44 ± 2.31	77.43 ± 1.11	90.16 ± 1.12
F7	12.72 ± 1.03	14.96 ± 2.04	20.44 ± 2.34	23.32 ± 2.10	40.99 ± 1.07	48.43 ± 1.34	42.18 ± 2.09	46.20 ± 1.14	62.73 ± 2.10	67.40 ± 2.30	72.44 ± 2.21	79.47 ± 1.01	88.00 ± 1.00
F8	14.32 ± 2.07	23.83 ± 1.08	32.40 ± 1.10	36.77 ± 2.16	48.22 ± 1.02	43.16 ± 0.97	44.94 ± 1.98	49.44 ± 2.33	64.92 ± 1.31	69.49 ± 1.09	72.33 ± 1.48	74.49 ± 2.07	86.27 ± 2.04
F9	14.32 ± 1.99	24.82 ± 1.11	32.42 ± 1.12	34.30 ± 2.10	40.94 ± 1.07	47.32 ±2.10	42.42 ± 1.13	47.41 ± 2.13	61.02 ± 1.44	64.04 ± 2.03	69.46 ±1.94	74.77 ± 1.07	84.13 ± 1.06

Each value represents mean ±SD (n=3)

Figure 6- In-vitro permeation profile from Transdermal patches-F1, F2, F3

Figure 7-In vitro permeation profile from Transdermal patches-F4, F5, F6

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, from the various methods available for TDDS preparation, the solvent casting method was selected for present work due to its simplicity. The physical parameters of drug as well as excipients concluded that these were considerably good to formulate the Transdermal patch. The polymers HPMC and EC were used for preparing the patch and oleic acid used as penetration enhancer. The patches prepared with polymers alone were found to be brittle. To prevent embrittlement a plasticizer, Propylene Glycol, a water soluble plasticizer, was chosen in the study in various concentration. The plasticizer diffuses in to and soften the polymer particles. This softening promotes the soft patch formation. The lower concentration of Propylene Glycol was found to give rigid and brittle patch where higher concentrations gave very soft patch. The suitable concentration of 20% of plasticizer was found to be better fitted for preparing the patch, hence selected for all formulations. Various methods such as IR spectroscopy, DSC analysis, TLC were used frequently to study the drug polymer interaction. The IR spectrum can accurately clarify the drug excipient interactions at various functional groups between drug and polymer mixture. Thus, the different peaks of drug polymer and their physical mixture indicate all groups and characteristics of drug are not altered. These studies revealed that there was no significant interaction between drug and polymer. The physicochemical compatibility of drug and polymer were also studied by differential scanning calorimetry(DSC). The DSC analysis of pure drug showed sharp endothermic peak at 204.61° corresponding to the drugs melting point. The IR and DSC spectroscopy results suggest that the drug and polymer are compatible for the preparation of Transdermal patch. The patches were evaluated for uniformity of weight. The results indicated that the prepared patches weights ranged from 31.4 ± 3.42 mg to 38.24 ± 3.20 mg whereas the thickness varied from 32.00 ± 1.00 to $49.33 \pm 2.41 \mu$. However, within a batch the patches were found to be uniform weight and thickness. The thickness of patches increases with increase in the concentration of polymer and decreases with decrease in concentration of polymer. The folding endurance was measured

manually to be ranged between 6.33 ± 0.48 to 9.33 ± 1.46 with high proportion of polymer showed increases in patch folding endurance due to its hydrophilic nature. The folding endurance test results indicated that the patches would not break and would maintain their integrity with general skin folding when applied.

The prepared patches were evaluated for the moisture uptake and moisture content. The highest moisture uptake of the patch F9 was found to be 7.13 ± 0.39 . Significant changes in properties of such as reduced crushing strength, increased total porosity and increased pore diameter of hydrophilic polymer containing polymer matrix due to moisture uptake. Thus, the low moisture uptakes of the prepared patches protect the formulations from microbial contamination and reduce bulkiness. The moisture uptake of the patches indicates that the patches may absorb a small amount of moisture in a high humid environment. The highest moisture content, among the various formulations, of the patch F9 was found to be 3.12 ± 0.18 . The moisture content of the prepared patches was also low which could help the formulations remain stable and reduce brittleness during long term storage. The moisture uptake and moisture content were found to be increase with increase in concentration of hydrophilic polymer. The prepared patches were evaluated for water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) studies. It was found to be 1.43×10^{-4} g/cm².24 h. at the 84 % RH for the patch F9 which is highest WVTR among the various formulations studied. The water vapor transmission studies indicate all the prepared patches were permeable to water vapour. These patches with low WVTR would act as occlusion to surface moisture on skin that might results in increased drug permeation for hydrophilic drug. Good uniformity of drug content among the batches was observed with all formulations and ranged from 88.07 ± 1.00 to 97.74 ± 1.34 %. The results indicated that method employed to prepare patches in this study was capable of producing patches with uniform drug content and minimum patch variability. The in vitro drug release studies were carried out for prepared Transdermal patches using phosphate buffer, pH 7.4. The release pattern of the patches showed initial fast release rate for the first one hour. The release rate was steady throughout the 24 h because of rate controlling membrane.

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